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Intermedial elements and synergies

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Introduction

This introduction serves to outline the hypotheses and methods utilized to investigate these hypotheses, that are employed in the exploration of intermedial elements and synergies within the realm of music composition. The main methods will be literature reviews, case studies and score analysis. I intent to examine different approaches by composers working with at least similar means.

After a short definition of what intermediality could be and a short overview of the history of piano instruments, I will focus on compositions that are about extending the piano sound through preparation or electronics. To establish theoretical frameworks, I will conduct a review of several essays that deal with the overlap between different arts, especially with regard to music and visual arts.

Being the main part of this thesis, there will be detailed analyses of *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* (2011 – 12) by Stefan Prins and *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* (2016/2018) by Michael Beil. These two works have in common the use of a piano or keyboard instrument in the broadest sense in combination with video projection. I will analyze the musical content of the pieces and examine, if the use of a visual medium might have influenced the writing of music, the performance and the perception.

I agree with Tim Shephard and Anne Leonard as they write that “art and music, as two major categories of creative production, have often been considered as two aspects of a single phenomenon ('culture'), and it is very seldom that developments affecting one of them would have left the other untouched.”¹ My intention is to discover the compositions in a way, that reaches beyond a purely music theoretical analyses, since music and any other art form is, in my opinion, at least partially always also an expression of the social, political and cultural circumstances in which we live.

¹ SHEPHARD and LEONARD 2014, Introduction.

1 Intermediality

We are clearly in a situation in which "interdisciplinarity in scholarship on music and visual culture [is] an inescapable reality."² Nevertheless it is still a relatively new phenomenon that arts also "began to affirm shared interests, areas of study, and methodological approaches."³

By the term "intermediality" I refer to a specific understanding of media combination or "synthetic intermediality"⁴ as for example found by Stefan Drees in his book *Körper Medien Musik. Körperdiskurse in der Musik nach 1950*. This understanding is based on the idea of a "synchronous processing of two or more media"⁵, whereby the "plurimedial basic structure becomes a specific feature of the new single medium that is created".⁶ Drees, quoting from *Intermedialität. Facetten und Probleme eines aktuellen medienwissenschaftlichen Begriffs*⁷ by Jens Schröter, writes:

"While in the case of *mixed media* the 'media forms that come together can at any time be viewed by the viewer as separate concepts', in the case of intermedia approaches a 'conceptual fusion' is determined, which absolutely requires the individual media components to be considered simultaneously, inseparably and related to one another."⁸

² SHEPHARD and LEONARD 2014, Introduction.

³ Ibid., Introduction.

⁴ DREES 2011, p. 44, orig.: "synthetischen Intermedialität", SCHRÖTER, JENS (1998). *Intermedialität. Facetten und Probleme eines aktuellen medienwissenschaftlichen Begriffs*, in: *motage/av* 7, H. 2, p. 130, translated by the author.

⁵ Ibid., p. 44, orig.: "synchronen Verarbeitung von zwei oder mehr Medien", translated by the author.

⁶ Ibid., p. 44, orig.: "... 'die plurimediale Grundstruktur zu einem Spezifikum des neu entstandenen ('Einzel')-Mediums wird.'", RAJEWSKI, IRINA O. (2002). *Intermedialität*, Francke, Tübingen, Basel, translated by the author.

⁷ 1998 in: *motage/av* 7, H. 2, p. 129–154.

⁸ Ibid., pp. 44–45, orig.: "Während im Falle der *mixed media* die 'medialen Formen, die in ihr zusammentreten, jederzeit vom Betrachter als getrennte begriffen werden können', ist für die von Grund auf intermedialen Ansätze eine 'konzeptuelle Fusion' bestimmend, die es geradezu zwingend voraussetzt, die einzelnen medialen Bestandteile als gleichzeitig, untrennbar und aufeinander bezogen zu betrachten.", translated by the author.

Concerning the different media, this ultimately also means, that "specific characteristics not only appear together but ideally cannot be separated from one another, without the entirety being destroyed."⁹

Drees writes that through its characteristics intermedial art can create an experience that points to "conventionalized patterns of perception and behavior in everyday life"¹⁰ and through which "habitual forms of perception can be broken through by opening up an expanded discourse on perception." This makes it possible "to disrupt clichés of production and behavior towards [...] already known things."¹¹

Especially from this point of view, it seems evident to refer to the piano. The piano has a long history of performance practice and perception and therefore clearly challenges composers to break through these habitual performance practices and perceptions. Two works in which this is done by using intermedial approaches will be discussed in this thesis.

⁹ DREES 2011, p. 44, orig.: "..., spezifische Merkmale nicht nur gemeinsam auftreten, sondern sich im Idealfall nicht voneinander trennen lassen, ohne dass dadurch die Gesamtheit zerstört wird.", translated by the author.

¹⁰ Ibid., p. 45, orig.: "konventionalisierte Wahrnehmungs- und Verhaltensmuster des alltäglichen Lebens", translated by the author.

¹¹ Ibid., p. 45, orig.: "Klischees der Produktion und des Verhaltens gegenüber [...] schon bekannten Dingen zu stören.", BAECKER, INGE (1975) *Nam Junge Paik*, in: *Sehen um zu hören. Objekte & Konzerte zur visuellen Musik der 60er Jahre. 17.10.–26.10.'75, Städtische Kunsthalle Düsseldorf. Cage, Kagel, Paik-Moorman, Chiari, Jones, Schnebel, Van Huene*, Städtische Kunsthalle Düsseldorf, p. 61, translated by the author.

2 Keyboard Instruments

Composers and performers usually depend on the nature of the instruments they write for or play. With the nature of the instruments, the way of playing and writing music also changes. Some composers or performers, who have the skills and the means, might even spend some effort on building their own instruments in order to use them specifically for their needs. More often, though, composers deal with instruments as they are.

In contemporary music the piano is rarely played only on the keys. The way of playing it and its sonority are important aspects in the compositions, discussed in this thesis. I decided to focus on works which use the piano, as in my opinion, the piano serves as an excellent example. It embodies both: tradition and versatility, being one of the most enduring and adaptable instruments.

In general the piano has an expansive sonic palette and is capable of producing a wide range of sounds, still it is limited in some other aspects. Composers can push the boundaries of their creative practice and forge new artistic territories for example by challenging traditional notions of what constitutes a piano composition.

The term "keyboard instrument" nowadays includes a bunch of instruments that are not only different in terms of their design but also in their mechanisms and sounds. Keyboard instruments therefore are among the most diverse instruments and as a result, their history is extensive. Perhaps it makes sense to see the development of the piano not as a straight line, but to recognize the diversity of different instruments. With this I am referring to Michael Latham, who in *Towards a new history of the piano. A context for the work of Johann Andreas Stein as a piano maker* writes:

"In the present book, this evolutionary approach is rejected. A history of the early piano is thus offered that respects the work of each maker, not as a step in a development but as a creative contribution."¹²

¹² LATHAM 2019, p. 7.

Though, since the concert piano has not changed significantly since the 19th century – Latcham emphasizes this by the way too¹³ – one can certainly also speak of an evolutionary development towards the modern concert piano. But if we look at earlier centuries, we will see that they contain a variety of different keyboard instruments that were different in their mechanisms and sounds and stood rather side by side in heterogenous plentitude.¹⁴ I think, nowadays we are in a similar situation. When we say "keyboard instrument", it could well be a traditional concert piano, but also a prepared concert piano, a MIDI keyboard, a cembalo, a synthesizer or an organ and the differences in their sound qualities are not subtle at all.

Compared to the creation of music in general, the history of piano music might still appear as a comparatively short period of time. However, for contemporary composers it is a challenge to be confronted with over 300 years of history, during which an instrument has been developed into a suitable instrument – if we set the starting point of piano music around 1700 – and during which one might say that the maximum of sound and virtuosity has probably been brought out of this instrument. Nevertheless, technological advancements can be seen very clearly on the piano. While in *Typologie du regard n°1 – Résonances pour piano et bande son. commande du concours national de piano d'Orléans "Brin d'herbe"* (2009) by Pierre Jodlowksi, a regular concert piano is played, Stefan Prins uses a MIDI keyboard for *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* (2011–12) and Michael Beil only uses an empty table top as "keyboard instrument" for *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* (2016/2018).¹⁵

¹³ See: LATCHAM 2019, p. 8.

¹⁴ See: Ibid., p. 8.

¹⁵ In private communication (mail), M. Beil mentioned, that the actual year *Key Jack* was created was 2017, because it was first played in January 2017. However, the score was already finished in 2016. Later he made a version for women where the spoken passages were produced with a woman's voice. When performing women were welcome but not obliged to call the piece *Key Jane*.

2.1 A short historical overview

In this chapter I would like to name just a few of the most important instrument makers and their new inventions. A detailed history cannot be possible in this context and is of no interest, as there are already plenty of them, e.g., as in the already mentioned *Towards a new history of the piano. A context for the work of Johann Andreas Stein as a piano maker* by Michael Latcham, on whose depiction I will rely, without much comparison to other views as this would go beyond the scope of this work and is not the focus of this work.

Some names to mention, when speaking about important instrument makers in the context of the piano, are Bartolomeo Cristofori and Johann Andreas Stein, who contributed to the development of the piano with the hammer mechanism¹⁶ as well as Sébastien Erard, with whom the history of the piano entered the nineteenth century, where the developments "led to the end of the tradition in which pianos were built with the hammer action invented by Stein."¹⁷

It is not entirely clear where to actually set the starting point for the history of the piano. According to Michael Latcham, "the invention of the piano by Bartolomeo Cristofori is dated around 1700."¹⁸ This piano consisted of "a set of tuned strings, a bridge, a soundboard and a keyboard of the same pattern as today."¹⁹ But these elements also existed "in harpsichords of long before Cristofori's time".²⁰ Latcham also writes that "for much of the eighteenth century, the piano and the harpsichord were not rivals. Both were thought of as harpsichords, one with plectra, the other with hammers."²¹ Yet, the decisive new invention, the "hammer action"²² made it possible to create dynamic variation through

¹⁶ LATCHAM 2019, p. 7.

¹⁷ Ibid., p. 8.

¹⁸ Ibid., p. 7.

¹⁹ Ibid., p. 7.

²⁰ Ibid., p. 7.

²¹ Ibid., p. 9.

²² Ibid., p. 7.

touch²³ and playing with dynamic variation "was often counted as an essential means for playing with expression."²⁴

It might be interesting to discuss how dynamical expression is done, if the instrument is not an acoustic touch-sensitive instrument, but for example a MIDI keyboard as in *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* by Stefan Prins, and how the possibility or impossibility to produce a dynamic expression might effect the player and the listener.

Apart from a very long development, the 19th century plays an important role in the history of the piano for several reasons: In the introduction of *The Cambridge Companion to the Piano* David Rowland states that by the 19th century "Virtuosos of the piano emerged who achieved celebrity status in their public performances."²⁵ With that "the necessity of finding ways of making the piano louder became more pressing"²⁶ and "the preferences of famous players had to be taken into account."²⁷ Also "competition became widespread."²⁸ The popularity of the piano led to the fact, that instrument makers were now "working on some sort of production line, turning out fifty or more instruments each year"²⁹ and "competition among piano makers was one of the factors that led to uniformity."³⁰

The craftsmanship of instrument making has also always been a field of creative activity. Some rather rare examples can be admired in museums and even today piano manufacturers implement new technologies and aesthetic visions. Attempts to create new keyboard instruments in history and today also often had or have to do with different tunings. Clearly most of these instruments remain exceptions. That has among other

²³ LATCHAM 2019, p. 7.

²⁴ Ibid., p. 7.

²⁵ ROWLAND 1998, 2000, p. 2.

²⁶ LATCHAM 2019, p. 7.

²⁷ Ibid., p. 7.

²⁸ Ibid., p. 7.

²⁹ Ibid., p. 7.

³⁰ Ibid., p. 8.

reasons probably also to do with the unfamiliar style of playing and the small repertoire for these instruments. I therefore guess, that it is more or less safe to say that the concert piano has reached its final form in the 19th century as it "has remained essentially unchanged since the first half of the nineteenth century."³¹

³¹ HARMS and HOLLAND 1998, p. 20.

3 Repertoire I

The fact that the piano remained unchanged might also have to do with the wealth of repertoire written for the modern concert piano. However, it must be said that most of the repertoire belongs rather to the classic or romantic era of music history. The piano as a solo instrument seems to play a less important role in contemporary music, whereas for other instruments there is a plethora of books in which modern playing techniques are discussed.

The piano has many advantages such as being a melody and harmony instrument. Music for piano can take on orchestral complexity. In fact, the piano is better suited to polyphonic playing than any other instrument. It can be an accompanying instrument and a solo instrument.

In my opinion, a specific characteristic of piano music is a particularly high degree of virtuosity. We can see that for example in the immense amount of etudes that have been written for the piano. Etudes aren't always pure exercises that focus on technical aspects. They often have qualities of real concert pieces. Maybe a comparison of playing techniques in etudes across the epochs in music history could also provide information about the developments of the instrument making itself. We will also find some stereotypical playing techniques in the pieces that I will examine later.

In summary, the piano is an excellent instrument for aspects such as virtuosity and harmony, but it is very limited in other aspects, e.g., the production of sounds other than well-tempered tones. Monika Fürst-Heidtmann writes in *Das präparierte Klavier des John Cage*, that pitch is always particularly predominant in the piano, but that it was precisely this parameter that was increasingly questioned towards the end of the 19th century.³²

In addition to frequently used playing techniques in contemporary piano music such as hitting different parts of the piano with different objects, plucking and bowing the strings

³² See: FÜRST-HEIDTMANN 1979, p. 2.

and so on, the preparation of the piano is probably the most common way to extend its well tempered and pitch centered sound. Also preparation can be a helpful tool to mark the nodes on the strings where overtones are produced or preparation can be used to entirely mute the strings in order to create percussion-like noises.

3.1 Music for prepared piano. John Cage's Sonatas and Interludes

In this chapter I will mostly refer to Monika Fürst-Heidtmann as she has carried out a fairly detailed study of prepared piano sounds in *Das präparierte Klavier des John Cage*. Since I could only find the German edition of the book, I will translate the most important ideas and refer to the relevant passages.

In the preface to *Das präparierte Klavier des John Cage*, Monika Fürst-Heidtmann writes that along with the foray into new harmonic realms the piano has also become a medium of experiment.³³

We usually refer to the piano as a "keyboard instrument". But from an instrument making perspective it is also, in a sense, a "string instrument" and a "percussion instrument". Monika Fürst-Heidtmann describes that John Cage "invented" the prepared piano around 1940 in connection with his work as a pianist accompanist and composer for a dance troupe when facing the problem that there was only room for a piano, but in order to create the idea of African music he needed a percussion ensemble. Due to the lack of a percussion ensemble, Cage alienated the piano sound using all sorts of materials put between the strings of the piano with materials mainly from everyday life such as screws and bolts, which produced a sound that is close to the percussion timbre.³⁴

On the next page you will see a list of preparation information for Cage's *Sonatas and Interludes*. As we can see in the preparation table, some tones are prepared only once with one material, other strings are prepared twice with different materials in different places, others are prepared in three different places with partly identical materials such as two screws and one rubber and others are even prepared with combinations of different materials in the same place.

³³ See: FÜRST-HEIDTMANN 1979, preface.

³⁴ See: Ibid., p. 40.

TONE	MATERIAL	STRINGS LEFT TO RIGHT	DISTANCE FROM BRIDGE (IN MEAS.)	MATERIAL	STRINGS LEFT TO RIGHT	DISTANCE FROM BRIDGE (IN MEAS.)	MATERIAL	STRINGS LEFT TO RIGHT	DISTANCE FROM BRIDGE (IN MEAS.)	TONE	
16va				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				A	
				MED. BOLT	2-3	1 3/8"				G	
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				F	
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				E	
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				D	
				SM. BOLT	2-3	2"				C	
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				B	
				FURNITURE BOLT	2-3	2 1/2"				B	
				SCREW	2-3	2 1/2"				A	
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				A	
				MED. BOLT	2-3	2 1/4"				G	
				SCREW	2-3	3 1/4"				F	
				SCREW	2-3	2 1/2"				F	
		SCREW	1-2	3 3/4"	FURN. BOLT + NUTS	2-3	2 1/2"	SCREW + 2 NUTS	2-3	3 1/4"	F
					SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				F
	8va				FURNITURE BOLT	2-3	1 1/2"				E
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				C	
				SCREW	2-3	1 1/2"				C	
				MED. BOLT	2-3	3 1/2"				B	
				SCREW	2-3	4 1/2"				A	
		RUBBER	1-2-3	4 1/2"	FURNITURE BOLT	2-3	1 1/2"			G	
					SCREW	2-3	1 3/4"			F	
					SCREW	2-3	2 1/2"			F	
		RUBBER	1-2-3	5 1/4"						E	
		RUBBER	1-2-3	6 1/2"	FURN. BOLT + NUT	2-3	6 7/8"			E	
					FURNITURE BOLT	2-3	2 1/2"			D	
		RUBBER	1-2-3	3 5/8"						D	
					BOLT	2-3	7 1/2"			C	
					BOLT	2-3	2"			B	
		SCREW	1-2	10"	SCREW	2-3	1"	RUBBER	1-2-3	8 1/4"	B
		(PLASTIC (over G))	1-2-3	2 9/16"				RUBBER	1-2-3	4 1/2"	G
	PLASTIC (OVER UNDER)	1-2-3	2 7/8"				RUBBER	1-2-3	10 1/8"	G	
	(PLASTIC (over D))	1-2-3	4 1/4"				RUBBER	1-2-3	5 1/2"	F	
	PLASTIC (OVER 1 - UNDER 2-3)	1-2-3	4 1/8"				RUBBER	1-2-3	9 3/4"	D	
	BOLT	1-2	15 1/2"	BOLT	2-3	1 1/2"	RUBBER	1-2-3	14 1/2"	D	
	BOLT	1-2	14 1/2"	BOLT	2-3	7/8"	RUBBER	1-2-3	6 1/2"	C	
	BOLT	1-2	14 3/4"	BOLT	2-3	9/16"	RUBBER	1-2-3	24"	B	
	RUBBER	1-2-3	9 1/2"	MED. BOLT	2-3	10 1/8"				B	
	SCREW	1-2	5 7/8"	LG. BOLT	2-3	5 7/8"	SCREW + NUTS	1-2	1"	A	
	BOLT	1-2	7 1/2"	MED. BOLT	2-3	2 1/4"	RUBBER	1-2-3	4 1/8"	A	
	LONG BOLT	1-2	8 3/4"	LG. BOLT	2-3	3 1/4"				G	
				BOLT	2-3	1 1/2"				D	
8va, 6va	SCREW + RUBBER	1-2	4 7/8"							D	
16va, 8va	ERASER (OVER 2 - UNDER 1, 4, 5)	1	6 3/4"							D	

* MEASURE FROM BRIDGE.

Table 1: CAGE. "Table of Preparations", in: *Sonatas and Interludes*.

In my opinion, the preparation material itself is characterized primarily by the fact that it is either a very hard material (screws, nuts) or a very soft material (rubber, eraser) or a medium-soft/medium-hard material (plastic). If the tones are three-fret string choirs, the list also contains information about which strings the preparation should be placed between, and in inches Cage provides information about the distance of each preparation from the dampers.

However, Monika Fürst-Heidtman notes, that in most of the pieces Cage does not provide any specific information about the type of instrument and "since every brand has a different dimension, [...] the preparation of two different grand pianos also leads to different sound results."³⁵

Monika Fürst-Heidtmann took a closer look at the preparation sounds more closely. We can see the results of this investigation in Fig. 1 on the next page. In general, it should be noted that "the perception of a concise, defined pitch correlates with a periodic oscillation line, which appears in discretely arranged partial tones when viewed spectrally"³⁶ as in Fig. 1 or Fig. 2. Since the partials are closer together in Fig. 2 than in Fig. 1, the impression is that of a "mixed sound, respectively an interval with pitches that are well to determine."³⁷ On the other hand, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show an unstructured and unspecific spectral structure. The pitch can only be recognized approximately (Fig. 6) or not at all (Fig. 7). The sound then is perceived as noise.³⁸ A sharp drop in the spectral envelope, such as in Fig. 3 "causes listening impressions that are primarily perceived as dull."³⁹

³⁵ FÜRST-HEIDTMANN 1979, p. 43, orig.: "Da aber jedes Fabrikat andere Maße hat [...], führt eine Präparation von zwei verschiedenen Flügeln auch zu unterschiedlichen Klangergebnissen.", translated by the author.

³⁶ Ibid., p. 66, orig.: "Die Wahrnehmung einer prägnanten, definierten Tonhöhe korreliert mit einem periodisch verlaufenden Schwingungszug, der sich bei spektraler Betrachtung in diskret angeordneten Teiltönen zeigt.", translated by the author.

³⁷ Ibid., p. 66, orig.: "Mischklang bzw. Intervall mit gut bestimmbaren Tonhöhen", translated by the author.

³⁸ See: Ibid., p. 67.

³⁹ Ibid., p. 67, orig.: "... löst Höreindrücke aus, die vornehmlich als dumpf empfunden werden.", translated by the author.

Fig. 1: "Klangspektren präp. Klaviertöne", in: FÜRST-HEIDTMANN 1979, p.68.

Another way of extending the piano or any other instrumental sound is to use electronics. In the next chapter I will have a look at *Typologie du regard n°1 – Résonances pour piano et bande son. commande du concours national de piano d'Orléans "Brin d'herbe"* (2009) by Pierre Jodlowksi.

3.2 Piano and audio playback. Pierre Jodlowksy's *Typologie du regard* N°1

The challenges of electronic music notation aren't new. In *Komposition im 20. Jahrhundert. Details – Zusammenhänge*, Walter Gieseler wrote a chapter about scores of electronic music, mentioning some of the problems.⁴⁰

One problem would be that pitches can't necessarily be captured by using the traditional tone material in a traditional system. Walter Gieseler claims, that if the electronic material should be specified precisely, an option would be to do it in frequencies⁴¹ as for example done in Stockhausen's *Studie II* (1954), which, according to Walter Gieseler, was the first fully executed attempt of an electronic score.⁴² In addition to pitch, the other basic parameters are also difficult to display: "Tone durations can no longer determined by a metronome or basic counting units"⁴³, "the indication of the volume no longer relies on an approximate forte or piano, but is measured exactly in decibels",⁴⁴ and "how timbres can be represented visually is extremely controversial".⁴⁵ Gieseler mentions that notation may not be necessary as long as it is purely electronic tape music, but that "the demand for an adequate score becomes unavoidable when electronic sounds from the tape have to be combined with real vocal or instrumental sounds."⁴⁶

Composers are not tied to traditional notation, not even in the notation of instrumental pieces. Many – also instrumental – sounds make pitch notation obsolete. There are diverse approaches to notation. We usually expect that a sound is notated, but also an action can be

⁴⁰ See: GIESELER 1975, pp. 182–187.

⁴¹ See: Ibid., p. 183, orig.: "Es bleibt, wenn das elektronische Material ganz exakt bestimmt werden soll, nur die exakte Zahlenangabe in Frequenzen."

⁴² See: Ibid., p. 183: "Der erste ganz ausgeführte Versuch einer elektronischen Partitur ist mit STOCKHAUSENS 'Studie II' (1954) erschienen (*F 5.1*)."

⁴³ Ibid., p. 182, orig.: "Die Tondauern sind nicht mehr durch Metronom und Grundzähleinheit bestimmt", translated by the author.

⁴⁴ Ibid., p. 182, orig.: "Die Angabe der Lautstärken verläßt sich nicht mehr auf ein ungefähres forte oder piano, sondern wird exakt nach Dezibel gemessen.", translated by the author.

⁴⁵ Ibid., p. 182, orig.: "Wie Klangfarben optisch dargestellt werden können, ist äußerst umstritten.", translated by the author.

⁴⁶ Ibid., p. 182: "Die Forderung nach einer zureichenden Partitur wird aber dann unausweichlich, wenn sich elektronische Klänge vom Tonband mit real ausgeführten vokalen oder instrumentalen Klängen zu verbinden haben.", translated by the author.

notated. We can find numerous of such action notations in Lachenmann, for example in *Guero* for piano (1969).⁴⁷ But also in electronic music, action notation could be used, for example, operating a fader. In addition, instructions can also be given in words. As with many things in contemporary music, individual solutions are often required.

Click tracks are often used to coordinate temporal processes between instrumentalists and audio-playbacks. A click track has advantages and disadvantages. Some musicians believe that the musicality would suffer as a result and that it is tedious to have a rigorous conductor in the ear. Nevertheless, when it comes to the accuracy of interpretations, I have had rather good experiences with click tracks. In *Key Jack* the click track plays a very important role, as it not only provides information on tempo, but also instructions on how and what to do or play and these spoken instructions partially replace the score as the piece must be played entirely from memory. However, if there is no click track, the electronic part has to be notated somehow clear enough, so that the instrumental performer can play with it.

Playing with additional electronics is a complex matter anyway. In the case of fixed media I try to think of the fixed media as another player. But that player doesn't react or adapt as a human player would do. It is therefore in most cases the responsibility of the performer to be accurate with the electronics. The use of electronics often requires additional people such as technicians, sound engineers, etc., yet not all concert organizers can guarantee this technical support and not all composers or performers have the luxury of a private sound engineer. There is therefore maybe already the tendency to create a niche within a niche.

Concerning the piano composition, chosen as an example for this chapter, Jodlowski writes: "This serie [sic!] of piano pieces is specially dedicated to piano students and is based on an exploration of relations between instrument and electronic sound."⁴⁸ Furthermore he explains that "This music has been conceived in order to be performed

⁴⁷ See: GIESELER 1975, p. 187.

⁴⁸ See: JODLOWSKI 2009, execution note.

easily [sic!]; the soundtrack is provided on a simple audio CD and the minimum technical requirement is a CD player, an amplifier and two loudspeakers."⁴⁹

He describes two possible configurations: one with amplification of the piano and one without:

Fig. 2: JODLOWSKI. *Typologie du regard n°1: Résonances*, acoustic version.

Fig. 3: JODLOWSKI. *Typologie du regard n°1: Résonances*, amplified version.

For the amplified version, Jodlowski also notes that a sound engineer should help with the amplification.⁵⁰ Another note concerns balance:

⁴⁹ See: JODLOWSKI 2009, execution note.

⁵⁰ See: Ibid., execution note.

"The balance between the acoustic sound of the piano and the soundtrack must be very precise in order to achieve a good performance. On the concert-CD, the first track provides a piano recording (C-note played mezzo-forte) ; the musician should play himself the same note at the same dynamic in order to ajust [sic!] the level of the soudtrack [sic!]. There is also, on the third track of the CD a simulation of the result of the piece with an electronic piano which could help to fix levels."⁵¹

Jodlowski's approach of keeping the use of electronics as simple as possible in terms of technical feasibility makes it easier for musicians who are not experts in electronics, and is therefore less elitist. It is also less tied to specific institutions or concert halls with extensive or expensive technical equipment.

⁵¹ See: JODLOWSKI 2009, execution note.

3.3 Score analysis

I would like to examine the piece in particular with regard to the notation of the fixed media and take a closer look on how electronic and instrumental sounds are interacting. Jodlowski writes the fixed media into a traditional "piano system", consisting of treble and bass clefs, which is helpful to show precise pitches, durations and volumes:

Example 1: JODLOWSKI. *Typologie du regard n°1 : Résonances*, beginning.

While we already have a very clear idea of the sound when we see the piano part, the notation for the fixed media – although very precise – remains an approximation. In this case the notation gives us an idea about pitch and duration of the fixed media but tells us nothing about other parameters, that are particularly important when it comes to electronic sounds, such as timbre, sharpness or softness, filter, etc.

The pianist has some time (~2") to start the CD before starting to play. Getting started is made easy by the musical monophony at the beginning of the piano part. One hand can start the CD, the other is ready to play. The *b flat* after the whole-step glissando marks clearly the 3rd beat of the first 4/4 bar and shortly after that, the pianist begins to play. The piano voice could therefore be understood as a response or reaction to the electronic sound, with which the piece begins. Something similar happens in the 4th bar after the insertion of a 7/4 bar. This insertion is a small interruption with pauses, after which the beginning motif (whole-tone glissando in the fixed media) is picked up again, including a slightly varied

"response" or "reaction" in the piano part. The piano part is much more figurative (e.g., bar 6&7), while the fixed media consists of longer sustained sounds that build a soundscape over which the piano can shine:

Example 2: JODLOWSKI: *Typologie du regard n°1 : Résonances*, bars 5–8.

The sounds of the playback are synthetic sounds. It is easy for the listener to differentiate between the electronics and the live instrument. In bar 8, the initial motif, with which the piece began (whole-step upwards in the electronics), is repeated for the 3rd time. A second voice is added in the electronics (bar 7&8). This kind of repetition and variation is common practice. In this rather quiet beginning and throughout the whole piece there are occasional accents that occur almost synchronously in the playback and the piano (1st beat bar 8) or as in Example 3, bar 20:

Example 3: JODLOWSKI: *Typologie du regard n°1 : Résonances*, bars 19–21.

In both cases the accent is prepared in the playback. In bar 8 it is done by a crescendo that starts in bar 7 in the playback and in bar 20 the accent in the playback appears slightly earlier, so that the instrumental player again is reacting to it. In bar 20 we also hear again the whole tone motif that has also appeared already in bar 12, supplemented there by a lower octave as another type of variation or modification of the sound:

Example 4: JODLOWSKI: *Typologie du regard n°1 : Résonances*, bars 12–14.

This motif appears again and again throughout this piece. The duration of the motif varies, and new voices are continually added. Sometimes the motif is also hidden in a glissando that starts on a lower pitch or continues to a higher pitch as in the following Example in bar 41&42:

Example 5: JODLOWSKI: *Typologie du regard n°1 : Résonances*, bars 41–45.

In summary, at this level of complexity, where durations and pitches are clearly perceptible, the use of the traditional staff system is a clear and comprehensible way for notating electronic sounds. In addition, this piece is easy to rehearse since it doesn't require much more than a CD player. As we could see, the piano is always connected to the playback. The piano reacts to the playback, though being much more figurative and widely spreading through registers. The playback sounds are rather perceived as background with occasional accents that go along with the piano.

4 Visual Art and Music

In the pieces that I will analyze in "Repertoire II" video is added which opens up an ever broader range of creative possibilities. In *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* and *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* we can find the attempt "to engage the eyes and ears in something like equal measure."⁵²

Two actually different arts have entered into a connection that I would define as "intermedial" art as described in Chapter 1. Therefore it is probably useful to integrate "the study of both arts into a new, synthesized understanding."⁵³

However, when trying to analyze either visual art or music or simultaneously both arts, we come across different means necessarily. Tim Shephard and Anne Leonard, editors of *The Routledge Companion to Music and Visual Culture* write:

"Art historians have over the years, quite reasonably, developed a range of specialized conceptual tools to help describe and explain visual art. In addition to the technical knowledge of materials and media necessary for visual analysis, the art historian may also take into consideration a variety of theoretical approaches pertaining to the status of the art object. The exclusivity of musical discourse, meanwhile, is greatly enhanced by the barrier presented to many by musical notation(s); and the language deployed within specialized music analysis is opaque even to many musicians."⁵⁴

When analyzing different art disciplines that come together we also have to take into consideration that "The histories of the disciplines (...) have by no means run in parallel."⁵⁵ Despite of these and other "challenges of cross-disciplinary research"⁵⁶ the editors of *The Routledge Companion to Music and Visual Culture* describe the contemporary situation as

⁵² SHEPHARD and LEONARD 2014, p. 2.

⁵³ Ibid., p. 2.

⁵⁴ Ibid., p. 1.

⁵⁵ Ibid., p. 1.

⁵⁶ Ibid., p. 3.

"a moment of great energy and productivity in the youthful field of music and visual culture."⁵⁷

⁵⁷ SHEPHARD and LEONARD 2014, p. 2.

4.1 Live Performances

A musical performance has in itself a strong performative and visual character. The audience is not only *listening* to live concerts, the audience is also *watching* a concert. In piano music we see virtuosos who nearly exhaust themselves in performance, while others might impress by the opposite, by their cool and reserved, almost majestic detachment. Their physical presence on stage is an important criterion for the evaluation of a performance. Visuality has always affected the audience's perception. In the end the audience doesn't only evaluate what is being presented acoustically but takes into regard the visual as well as the acoustic presentation. Otherwise the audience could listen with closed eyes, or the performer could play behind a curtain. It is therefore probably very well put to say:

"Music, in short, is not simply made, it is simultaneously *acted*. [...] When people hear a musical performance they see it as an embodied activity. What they hear they also witness: how the performers look, of course, but also how they are costumed, how they interact with their instruments and with one another, how they regard the audience, etc."⁵⁸

In *Seeing Music* Richard Leppert states, that "musicians' gestures commonly exceed the physical movements necessary to produce the wanted sounds."⁵⁹ This seems correct, when we look at some "facial expressions"⁶⁰ or the "general body language involving hands, arms, legs, and torso."⁶¹ Is it an unnecessary spectacle? Or do musicians "act out music somatically, [...] as a critical supplement to sonority"?⁶² Leppert speaks of "semiotic codes"⁶³ or more precisely:

"To render visually meaningful the acoustic phenomenon of music, the artist engages semiotic codes that operate as a sight when music is actually made. The

⁵⁸ LEPPERT 2014, p. 7.

⁵⁹ Ibid., p. 7.

⁶⁰ Ibid., p. 7.

⁶¹ Ibid., p. 7.

⁶² Ibid., p. 7.

⁶³ Ibid., p. 10.

artist doesn't invent a visual code entirely divorced from life-practice, for the simple reason that there is no point in doing so."⁶⁴

The pieces that I am going to evaluate in "Repertoire II" place a strong focus on the gestural nature of music performance and by doing that raise the question of whether this gestural nature is actually natural. I am again referring to Richard Leppert, who puts the act of gestural conventionalization in performances – which has clearly taken place also in piano music and in the general habits of classical and contemporary music performances –, into a discursive light: "By naturalizing modes of representation, conventions stabilize certain behaviours."⁶⁵ He states that "conventions are operative principles of order, just as order itself is the expression of power."⁶⁶ Knowing that, one could ask him- or herself: Do I like these operative principles of order and am I okay with submitting to this power, which is also an expression of "a particular way of life"?⁶⁷

Through exaggerating gestural conventions by duplicating them via video they become a motif and therefore accessible to discussion and reflection. Along with that, the question arises: What would happen if one skips or exaggerates the gestural convention? Are "Key Jack" or "Key Jane" caricatures? And what exactly is the heroic thing about the "Piano Hero"?

"[...] The rich array of caricatures relating to music, performance, and audience reception abundantly demonstrates this point, often with high degrees of trenchant social irony, commonly tinged with biting sarcasm."⁶⁸

Additionally the pieces do not only deal with gestural conventions, but also with musical conventions.

⁶⁴ LEPPERT 2014, p. 10.

⁶⁵ Ibid., p. 11.

⁶⁶ Ibid., p. 11.

⁶⁷ Ibid., p. 10.

⁶⁸ Ibid., p. 11.

4.2 Performance Practice and Culture

If we recognize that in art performances we automatically include the expression of "a particular way of life"⁶⁹, this is exactly what creates the connection to culture, or as Masha Morton puts it in her essay *Cultural History*: "Culture encompassed ways of life – social habits, and practices – and within these, the arts both high and low."⁷⁰

Let's say, there is a mutual interaction: On the one hand, arts and art performances are usually part of a certain cultural mentality; on the other hand, we experience "the arts as shapers of culture mentalities and productions"⁷¹.

Due to this reciprocal influence, the arts are particularly suitable for also critically questioning exactly those "social beliefs, habits and practices"⁷² of which they are themselves a part. Laura Cull mentions in her essay *Performance Studies* that "performance [...] is not only an object to be studied [...], but also operates as a valued research method in itself."⁷³

In piano music with its long, bourgeois tradition, "the courtship role of pianos in middle-class homes, and the conflict between the nineteenth century's silent concert etiquette and bodily impulses"⁷⁴ could be a theme of such a research carried out through a performance.

Referring to Peter Gay's *The Bourgeois Experience: Victoria to Freud*, Marsha Morton states that Peter Gay's work is a "cultural history of feelings, sensibilities, and tastes that synthesizes myriad sources to challenge stereotypes about a homogenous and repressed bourgeoisie."⁷⁵

⁶⁹ LEPPERT 2014, p. 11.

⁷⁰ MORTON 2014, p. 50.

⁷¹ Ibid., p. 58.

⁷² Ibid., p. 50.

⁷³ CULL 2014, p. 59.

⁷⁴ MORTON 2014, p. 54.

⁷⁵ Ibid., p. 53.

As already said, in *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* and *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* we can also find many stereotypes. We wouldn't even have to analyze the music for that. The stereotypes are already jumping at us in the titles: A "hero" is a stereotype in itself as well as a "Jack" or a "Jane". And the compositions do not only refer to a reflection of stereotypes of piano music. Through the inclusion of other media – produced "in the age of reproduction and modernizing media; the growth of institutions (museums, symphonies, galleries); collectors and consumers"⁷⁶ – they also deal with the role of these media. The composers show dependences on several levels by making the pieces work only through these dependences.

⁷⁶ MORTON 2014, p. 54.

4.3 Video Art

Since one of the most important components of the works I will discuss in Chapter 5 is the use of a visual medium in the context of music, I would like to briefly take a separate look at what video generally and additionally brings to the table. Holly Rogers states in her essay *Multimedia Art. Video Art-Music* that "video art is often considered a visual genre"⁷⁷ but that the perhaps most revolutionary achievement was that "the electromagnetic basis of the video format enabled sound and image to be recorded and projected simultaneously in an easy, portable way."⁷⁸

The fact that "film technology provided a significant boost to the possibility of 'musicalized time' as it enabled the static image to burst into time"⁷⁹ seems to make the video a perfect interface between composers and visual artists, since "early video technology provided artists with the opportunity to easily sound their visual work, and composers the means by which to visualize their music."⁸⁰ Holly Rogers states that video art made it possible to "produce a live form of audiovisual synergy rarely possible before."⁸¹

Aside from being an interface of previously largely separate art disciplines, video had several other advantages. For example, video was rather "cheap and easy to use: it could be managed by one person; it could manipulate sound and image in real time; it could use the space around it as a creative material; and it could engender a new mode of activated spectatorship."⁸²

I've been hearing the term "immersive" a lot lately. It can be true that through processing visual information and acoustic information at the same time, the audience on the one hand

⁷⁷ ROGERS 2014, p. 367.

⁷⁸ Ibid., p. 367.

⁷⁹ Ibid., p. 367.

⁸⁰ Ibid., p. 370.

⁸¹ Ibid., p. 367.

⁸² Ibid. p. 367.

as listener and viewer but also the composers as creators of such audio-visual works could for example use it as an opportunity to develop new "strategies of listening and viewing."⁸³ Holly Rogers states, that "when displayed, video could immerse artist, performer, and audience within a single, interactive environment."⁸⁴

In Holly Rogers' essay we can find several examples of early video works. She for example mentions as some of many early video protagonists that began their careers as previously trained musicians, Nam June Paik (experimental composer), Steina Vasulka (classical violinist) and Robert Cahen (electro-acoustic composer). Further she mentions artists that didn't have an explicit musical training, but "an established working relationship with music"⁸⁵, among them Tony Conrad, La Monte Young, John Cale, Bruce Nauman and Bill Viola. Especially in the 1960's in New York the scene seems to have been quite enlivened:

"Nine Evenings: Theater and Engineering was a series of multimedia events staged at the 69th Regiment Armory, New York, during October 1966. Organized by Billy Klüver, an electrical engineer, *Nine Evenings* presented work created by New York artists and musicians, including Cage, Tudor, Robert Rauschenberg, Robert Whitman, and Merce Cunningham, in collaboration with engineers from the Bell Telephone Laboratories. By bringing music and art together with new technologies such as video, wireless sound transmission, closed-circuit television, Doppler sonar devices that could translate movement into sound, and infrared television cameras, Klüver hoped to develop integrated audiovisual performativity, [...]."⁸⁶

⁸³ ROGERS 2014, p. 368.

⁸⁴ Ibid., p. 368.

⁸⁵ See: Ibid., p. 367.

⁸⁶ Ibid., p. 370.

5 Repertoire II

After I defined the term intermediality in Chapter 1, clarified why the piano seems to me to be a suitable instrument as a basis for selecting the works in Chapter 2, discussed through case studies works that expand the piano sound without visual elements in Chapter 3 and established theoretical frameworks through literature reviews of relevant books and articles that relate particularly to the connection between the visual and the acoustic in Chapter 4, I would like to move on now to the main part of this thesis.

Michael Beil makes all of his compositions available for download on his homepage, also the material for *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* (2016/2018). Stefan Prins sent the material to me upon request. I can also base the analysis of *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* especially with regard to the technical aspects on a master's thesis from 2016 by Florian Bogner, who also was involved in the development, premiere and revision of the piece.⁸⁷

When analyzing the works, I will take following aspects into account: the technical equipment that is needed in order to perform the pieces. I will also have a look at the Max patches, the scores and the video and playback material. By looking at the individual components of the works I hope to come to an interpretation of the works as a whole.

An interpretation is never free from subjective interest or knowledge and therefore does not necessarily and never fully correspond to the intention of the composer. An interpretation is partly a statement about the viewer's or listener's experience. Incidentally, this also applies to all other arts. I personally have been particularly interested in gestural aspects of music production lately. In the field of electronics, in contrast to pure instrumental music, it is obvious that sound no longer needs to correspond to the gesture and video is a suitable medium to emphasize gesture.

⁸⁷ See: BOGNER 2016, p. 1.

Marsha Morton discusses an approach to understanding art, that I consider helpful: "Beginning in the 1970s", she writes, "a theoretical turn in cultural history has significantly changed interpretations of the arts. [...], cultural expressions (signs, gestures, performances, artifacts, language) are now regarded as constructed, with symbolic meanings and values capable of being decoded [...]"⁸⁸

She also refers to Leppert, stating "[...] Leppert's primary concern is with music as visualized and embodied activity. [...]. Recurring topics, shared with art historians and new cultural historians, have included gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, the body, and emotion."⁸⁹

⁸⁸ MORTON 2014, p. 54.

⁸⁹ Ibid., p. 55.

5.1 Stefan Prins – Piano Hero #1

The full title of the cycle is *Piano Hero. An immersive cycle for midi-keyboard, grand piano, live cameras, video and live electronics*. It is commissioned by and dedicated to Frederik Croene.⁹⁰ In this cycle "the role of the classical concert pianist is expanded, questioned and caricatured."⁹¹ The pianist, as Florian Bogner describes in his master's thesis about Stefan Prins' cycle "Piano Hero", would increasingly lose control of his instrument when meeting "his virtual avatar, which competes with him".⁹²

According to Florian Bogner, Stefan Prins, a trained pianist himself⁹³, can be assigned to the generation of digital natives⁹⁴, which is characterized in the new music scene by the fact that for them "the use of the internet and computers is a matter of course".⁹⁵ Also performers adapt to given technical standards. Bogner writes: "Meanwhile it is common that for example a pianist who works with new music knows how to use special computer programs, synthesizers and MIDI keyboards."⁹⁶ Reluctance towards technical aspects would decrease:

The interaction with microphones and loudspeakers, [...], is more and more familiar to young performers and the separation between technicians and musicians at least partially be disappearing. Most ensembles understand the importance of technology

⁹⁰ See: https://www.stefanprins.be/eng/composesInstrument/comp_2011_01_pianohero.html, accessed 02.06.2024.

⁹¹ BOGNER 2016, p. 7, orig.: "Die Rolle des klassischen Konzertpianisten, [...] wird dadurch erweitert, in Frage gestellt und karikiert.", translated by the author.

⁹² Ibid., p. 7, orig.: "... seinen virtuellen Avatar [...], der mit ihm in Konkurrenz tritt", translated by the author.

⁹³ See: Ibid., p. 4.

⁹⁴ See: Ibid., p. 7.

⁹⁵ Ibid., p. 4, orig.: "... der Umgang mit dem Internet und dem Computer eine Selbstverständlichkeit ist [Schäfer 2013].", translated by the author.

⁹⁶ Ibid., p. 4, orig.: "Mittlerweile ist es üblich, dass z.B. ein Pianist, der sich mit Neuer Musik auseinandersetzt, auch weiß, wie spezialisierte Computerprogramme, Synthesizer und Midi Keyboards zu bedienen sind.", translated by the author.

and therefore have permanent live-electronic performers or sound engineers who increasingly specialize in the use of live electronics."⁹⁷

According to Bogner, this new generation of composers often bases their work on non-musical content:⁹⁸ "In several works Stefan Prins deals with the digitalization of society, the surveillance or hybridization of people and the resulting effects on our lives."⁹⁹ Bogner also mentions that the title *Piano Hero* also refers to the world of computer games and the video game *Guitar Hero*.¹⁰⁰

Bogner's questions also concern the notation of works with live electronics. He highlights issues such as that there are "no uniform standards for notation, additional information such as required equipment, playing instructions, documentation about the software or hardware as well as musical analyses are essential, but rarely provided systematically and completely."¹⁰¹ Above all he is concerned about ways of the documentation "in order to enable re-performability in the long term under changing technical conditions".¹⁰²

⁹⁷ BOGNER 2016, p. 4, orig.: "Die Interaktion mit Mikrofonen und Lautsprechern, [...], ist den jungen Interpreten vertraut, die Trennung zwischen Technikern und Musikern verschwindet so zumindest teilweise. Die meisten Ensembles sind sich der Wichtigkeit der Technologie bewusst und haben fixe Live-Elektronik-Performer oder Tonmeister, die sich in zunehmender Zahl auf den Umgang mit Live-Elektronik spezialisieren.", translated by the author.

⁹⁸ See: Ibid., p. 5.

⁹⁹ Ibid., p. 5, orig.: "Stefan Prins beschäftigt sich in mehreren Arbeiten mit der Digitalisierung der Gesellschaft, der Überwachung, oder Hybridisierung des Menschen und den dadurch entstehenden Auswirkungen auf unser Leben.", translated by the author.

¹⁰⁰ See: Ibid., p. 7, translated by the author.

¹⁰¹ Ibid., p. 2, orig.: "... keine einheitlichen Standards für Notation. Zusatzinformationen, wie benötigtes Equipment, Spielanweisungen für Interpreten und Klangregie, Dokumentation über die Software oder Hardware sowie musikalische Analysen sind essenziell, werden aber selten systematisch und vollständig zur Verfügung gestellt.", translated by the author.

¹⁰² Ibid., p. 1, orig.: "... um ihre Wiederaufführbarkeit auch bei wechselnden technischen Bedingungen langfristig zu ermöglichen", translated by the author.

5.1.1 MIDI keyboard as trigger surface for video samples

In this composition the pianist is not playing a piano, but a MIDI keyboard and by playing the MIDI keyboard video samples or certain processes, about which I will write later, are triggered. The MIDI keyboard itself is essentially a soundless instrument and can be programmed with all sorts of sounds or video material. The MIDI keyboard, according to the instructions of the composer, must have 88 keys and must be connected to a computer running the Max patch "PianoHero1".¹⁰³ In the textfile "_README-SETUP"¹⁰⁴ it is explained that all other devices must also be connected to the laptop, i.e., the MIDI keyboard, the sound card and the webcam:

Fig. 4: PRINS (2011). Stage Plan for Piano Hero #:1, p. 3.

¹⁰³ See: PRINS 2011, p. 1.

¹⁰⁴ See appendices: _README-SETUP in folder: PH1-Mac=S12-Max8.

In the stage plan we can see that the webcam is behind the pianist, the projection is more to the side of the pianist and the stereo sound and subwoofer comes rather from the direction of the video than from the performer's direction.

The Midi Keyboard is mapped as in Fig. 5:

Fig. 5: PRINS. *Piano Hero #1*, Performance Notes, p. 1.

We can see that most of the keys trigger previously recorded video samples (*f2–e5*), some keys process these files by means of transpositions (*c6–c8*) and one key changes the playback direction, another key turns the webcam on or off. With regard to further analysis, it must be mentioned that the designation of pitches differ. According to Prins, the video mapping is placed on the keys *f2–e5* (see Fig. 4), but in Bogner's table (see Table 3) we find the video mapping on *f1–e4*.

On p. 12 and on pp. 13–15 Florian Bogner shows detailed tables about the mapping of the midi keyboard. In the table in which the video files are listed we can see that many video files have a duration of less than 00:01 (MM:SS), i.e., that they are extremely short. By far the longest video file has a duration of only 01:01, otherwise only 8 of the 35 video files are longer than 00:01, most of them not much longer (00:03–00:05). Only very few files have a somewhat significantly longer duration with durations between 00:18–00:30.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁵ See: PRINS 2011, pp. 12, 13–15.

Tabelle 2: Piano Hero #1, Mapping der Samples auf dem Keyboard

Midi Note	Name des Files	Länge MM:SS	Play Mode	Abspielrate
F1	front-t6-1.mov	00:30	0	1
F#1	front-t6-2.mov	00:21	0	1
G1	front-t6-3.mov	00:18	0	1
G#1	front-t6-4.mov	01:01	0	1
A1	Frontal-take6-1-2.mov	00:25	1	1
A#1	front-take6-1-1-7.mov	00:01	1	1
B1	front-take6-1-1-4.mov	00:01	0	1
C2	front-take6-1-1-5.mov	<00:01	1	1
C#2	front-take6-1-1-6.mov	00:03	0	1
D2	front-take6-1-1-3.mov	00:01	1	1
D#2	front-take6-1-1-8.mov	00:01	0	1
E2	front-take6-1-1-9.mov	<00:01	0	1
F2	front-take6-1-1-14b.mov	<00:01	0	1
F#2	front-take6-1-1-15.mov	00:01	0	1
G2	front-take6-1-1-13.mov	00:01	0	-14
G#2	front-take6-1-1-24.mov	00:05	0	1
A2	front-t9-1-9.mov	00:03	0	0.1
A#2	front-t9-4-13.mov	00:01	0	0.06
B2	front-t6-4-draai2.mov	00:01	0	1
C3	front-take6-1-1-10-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
C#3	front-take6-1-1-11-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
D3	front-take6-1-1-18-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
D#3	front-take6-1-1-16-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
E3	front-take6-1-1-17.mov	00:01	1	1
F3	front-take6-1-1-12-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
F#3	front-take6-1-1-19-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
G3	front-take6-1-1-20-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
G#3	front-take6-1-1-22-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
A3	front-take6-1-1-23-1.mov	<00:01	0	1
A#3	front-take6-1-1-23-2.mov	<00:01	0	1
B3	front-take6-1-1-23-3.mov	<00:01	0	1
C4	front-take6-1-1-23-4.mov	<00:01	0	1
C#4	front-t6-4-n-2.mov	<00:01	1	1
D4	front-t6-4-n-1.mov	<00:01	1	1
D#4	front-t6-4-n-3.mov	00:01	1	1
E4	front-t6-4-n-4-longer.mov	00:03	1	1

Table 2: BOGNER. Mapping of the Midi Keyboard. pp. 13–15.

Another table shows that most transpositions have a randomness between a certain number of semitones. Only a few keys trigger a fixed transposition, for example the *C7* key, which always triggers a transposition of 64 semitones, or the *F5* key, which always triggers a transposition of 0 semitones, i.e., resets to the initial value:

Tabelle 1: Piano Hero #1, Mapping der Midi Noten zu ihren Funktionen im Patch

Midi Note¹⁰	Funktion
A-1/21	Schaltet das Bild der Webcam an und unterbricht die Videosamples
A#-1/22	Schaltet den Beamer schwarz
C#0/25	Startet ein Midi File
C#1/36	Schaltet die Abspielrichtung zwischen Vorwärts und Rückwärts
F1/41 bis E4/76	Startet die Audio- und Videosamples (siehe extra Tabelle)
C5/84	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen -55 und -34 Halbtönen
C#5/85	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen -34 und -21 Halbtönen
D5/86	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen -21 und -13 Halbtönen
D#5/87	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen -13 und -8 Halbtönen
E5/88	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen -8 und 0 Halbtönen
F5/89	Transposition um 0 Halbtöne (Reset auf den Initialwert)
G5/90-F6/101	Fixe Transposition um jeweils 1 Halbton bis zu 12 Halbtönen
F#6/102	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen 12 und 14 Halbtönen
G6/103	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen 14 und 17 Halbtönen
G#6/104	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen 17 und 22 Halbtönen
A6/105	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen 22 und 30 Halbtönen
A#6/106	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen 30 und 43 Halbtönen
B6/107	Transposition Zufallswert zwischen 43 und 64 Halbtönen
C7/108	Fixe Transposition um 64 Halbtöne

Table 3: BOGNER. Mapping of the Midi Keyboard, p. 12.

5.1.2 Max patch

In this chapter I will describe the surface of the main patch. The folder "PH1-Mac=S12-Max8" contains everything that is necessary to perform this piece. In this folder the first document appears to be a text document called "_README-SETUP". This document contains detailed instructions for running the patch. The main patch itself looks like a keyboard:

Fig. 6: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve" (presentation).

An earlier version of the Max patch, which is also included in the folder *PH1-Mac=S12-Max8*, looks like this:

Fig. 7: "PianoHero1-22May2012" (presentation).

In a private ZOOM communication, Florian Bogner mentioned that one of the main problems that needed to be solved was that the video engine no longer performed the transpositions associated with faster or slower playback speeds, so that the sound had to be separated from the video to maintain the effect of transposition.

Prins explains that "the latest version of MAX (for Mac)"¹⁰⁶ must be installed on the laptop, but that it would not be necessary to buy a licence, because the Max Patch would also work on the free version. Nevertheless, the question arises what "the latest version of MAX (for MAC)"¹⁰⁷ is at any given time. Prins writes: "The patch has been successfully tested on Mac OS 12.0.1 with Max8, and should also run on older OS and Max6 and Max7."¹⁰⁸ Further he instructs to "store the downloaded folder with the max patch for Piano Hero #1 on your computer where you want to keep it. Don't move any files outside of this main folder."¹⁰⁹ One reason for something not working in MAX can often be that some files, subpatches or abstractions are not found where they should be.

Prins has taken additional precautions: "double click the file "1-setpath.maxpat", Max 8 will then automatically open and close again (and will internally have changed a setting so that it should find all the files automatically next time you open it)".¹¹⁰ When the main patch (Fig. 5), is opened with a double click after a few seconds all video files should have been loaded. An extra button (see Fig. 8) allows to select the sound card:

Fig. 8: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", select soundcard.

¹⁰⁶ See appendices: _README-SETUP, in folder: PH1-Mac=S12-Max8.

¹⁰⁷ See: Ibid.

¹⁰⁸ See: Ibid.

¹⁰⁹ See: Ibid.

¹¹⁰ See: Ibid.

The next instruction is: "click ARM"¹¹¹

Fig. 9: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", ARM.

The color of the button changes from red to green, giving reassurance that it is working. Also there are movements in the numbers of frames per second (See Fig. 9). The display could also be changed to "ms", "type", "dim", "planes" or "name" (see Fig. 10). However, it is an illustrative display and must to be controlled or influenced during the performance by the performer.

Fig. 10: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", display settings.

The next instruction is: "in the SELECT INPUT window, click on the black button (with red circle), and select 'USB LOCAL WEBCAM' in the green dropdown menu. In the red dropdown menu underneath you select the name of the camera you will use."¹¹²

¹¹¹ See appendices: _README-SETUP in folder: PH1-Mac=S12-Max8.

¹¹² See: Ibid.

Fig. 11: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", input camera.

As last point Prins mentions, that "if necessary, you can adjust the proportions of the webcam image in the green window underneath the 'select input' window".¹¹³ Control is given over the zoom function, the start-x value and the start-y value:

Fig. 12: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", input camera.

Finally by pressing the space bar everything should run automatically.

In summary, it can be said that the patch itself is complex, especially when you exit the presentation mode and go into the deeper levels of the patch, but to operate the patch is rather simple. In fact, the performer only needs to press the space bar once at the beginning of the performance, after previously having stored and executed everything as described in the instructions, that can be found in the document "_README-SETUP".

A look into the "inside" of the patch reveals the actual "grammar" of the patch:

¹¹³ See appendices: _README-SETUP, in folder: PH1-Mac=S12-Max8.

Fig. 13: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", presentation mode off.

From this excerpt of the patch you can see, that the patch is structured into sections "MIDI STUFF", "Preset STUFF", "key STUFF", "VIDEO STUFF", "AUDIO STUFF" (see Figure 13) and another section, that didn't fit into the screenshot, which is "Presentation Mode Labels". The "MIDI STUFF" section is in particularly essential for the mapping of the keyboard:

Fig. 14: "PianoHero1-m7-fbog190327-webcam-solve", midi routing (excerpt).

5.1.3 Score analysis

Haize Lizarazu, a pianist, performer and artistic researcher, whose work I will refer to later again, writes:

"There are many different kinds of scores, ranging from traditional staff notation systems to graphical scores, to video- or aural-scores. All of them are related to sound and show us various ways of representing it. When digging into other artistic disciplines, however, such as dance, theatre or performance, we can also find the score concept—not related to sound, but to movement and/or actions."¹¹⁴

Both compositions, *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* (2011 – 12) by Stefan Prins and *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* (2016/2018) by Michael Beil, actually are written in "traditional staff notation".¹¹⁵

In *Piano Hero #1* we can also find articulation indications, which are "S2", (see Example 6, bar 72), meaning "as short as possible", "L", which means legato playing, and "S1", which is an articulation between legato and "S2".¹¹⁶

Example 6: PRINS. *Piano Hero #1*, bars 72–74.

In the score excerpt (Example 6) mainly two video files are triggered repeatedly in quick succession. We can find many fast and rhythmical repetitions, even tremolos, throughout the piece. Prins explains:

¹¹⁴ LIZARAZU 2022, p. 22.

¹¹⁵ Ibid., p. 22.

¹¹⁶ See: PRINS 2011, performance notes, p. 1.

"Each video sample is activated only as long as the key is being pressed. Therefore it's of critical importance that the rhythmical values to be found in the score are played as precisely as possible. That's why the 'articulation' also plays a crucial role."¹¹⁷

Analyzing the score, I will point out some key moments in the score that stood out to me either in notation or in relation to what we see in the video. The importance of gesture in *Piano Hero #1* can also be understood from the instruction that Prins gives us on page 2 of the performance notes of *Piano Hero #1*:

"It's of extreme importance that, if the pianist plays from a score, the score-stand should be positioned in such a way that the audience (even on the first row!) can still clearly see his fingers while playing."¹¹⁸

Playing the piano is usually associated with high virtuosity, so the visibility of the pianist's hands is important. The video *could* be used as a kind of magnifying glass of the pianist's fingers and hands, but here the video rather represents a counterpoint to the live performance as the virtual pianist does not play with fingers on keys at all. The "real" pianist is quite busy playing on keys, yet, during the entire first page the pianist plays only with the right hand. This extended monophony (Example 7) is rather atypical for piano playing. As I mentioned in a previous chapter, the piano stands out from other instruments, precisely because of its ability to create complex chords and polyphony.

MIDI keyboard

♩ = 92-100 (*)

S1

4:3b

Example 7: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 1&2.

¹¹⁷ See: PRINS 2011, p. 1.

¹¹⁸ Ibid., p. 2.

With only a few exceptions such as on the 2nd beat of the 2nd bar (Score Example 7) almost the entire first page has a continuous sixteenth note rhythm and a new video file is triggered with each sixteenth note. As a result, we as listeners and viewers are constantly confronted with new visual and acoustic information at a fairly rapid pace, which creates a forward momentum and driven restlessness. The sounds that we hear in the triggered video files are noisy sounds and have nothing to do with the well-tempered piano sound.

In addition of irregular tuplets as in the 2nd bar as interruption of the continuous regularity, there are also interruptions, caused by longer groups of grace notes or single grace notes, as in Score Example 8 in the 3rd and 4th bar:

Example 8: PRINS. – *Piano Hero #1*, bars 3&4.

These interruptions in the rhythmic regularity create the feeling of faltering or stumbling. Also we have a continuous 4/4 time signature on the entire first page with an exception in bar 9 (Example 9), which contains one sixteenth less:

Example 9: PRINS. *Piano Hero #1*, bars 8–10.

A subtraction of a short rhythmic value occurs also in other places and on the 2nd page of the score we will see irregularities much more often.

Piano Hero #1 begins with a rest (see Score Example 2), but the next rests appear not before bar 12:

Example 10: PRINS. *Piano Hero #1*, bars 11&12.

In the next section the rather continuously sixteenth notes disappear and in bar 14 (Example 11) the left hand is ultimately used for the first time:

Example 11: PRINS. *Piano Hero #1*, bars 13–16.

The moment in which the left hand is used for the first time also represents a special moment in the video. The virtual pianist drops the objects, previously held in his hands, onto the strings of the piano. While on the first page we had a 4/4 time signature, the second page consists of different time signatures, compound bars. Different kind of tremolos and tone repetitions, some of which are divided between both hands, appear more often, as can be seen in the next Examples:

Example 12: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 25–30.

In Example 12, the tone repetitions are notated as tremolo, a type of notation that is rarely found in piano repertoire and is more common with string or wind instruments. In Example 12 we also see the melody line of an audio file that runs independently of the rest and is started shortly before by pressing the key *D flat* (see Fig. 6–12 "FILE"). This adds another layer of sound that the pianist cannot influence once it is started.

Bar 35 (Example 13) is another interesting moment. The pianist is playing wild repetitions on the keyboard with both hands. The fast repetitions find a sudden end in bar 35 with a sustained note. It is precisely in this moment that the repetitions shift into the virtual image, because the held note causes the very short video file to be triggered again and again. Additionally, the articulation gradually changes from staccato to legato:

Example 13: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 31–35.

The composition continues to be more riddled with rests and sustained notes as in Example 14:

Example 14: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 36–40.

Soon after that the right hand moves into the register of the keyboard onto which the transpositions are mapped. Taking the different key nomenclature into account – (*c6*

PRINS = *C5/84* Bogner, see Fig. 5/Table 2) – we find the following transposition values here: random transposition value between -13 and -8 semitones on key *D#5/87*, random transposition value between -8 and 0 semitones on key *E5/88* and a transposition of 0 semitones on key *F5/89*, i.e. a reset to the initial value:

Example 15: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 46–49.

Speed is another essential element in composition. On the normal piano, in contrast to strings or wind instruments, it isn't possible to further shape or maintain a tone after the attack, and the dynamics of a piano decrease the longer the note is held. Here, however, a long held note has, as already mentioned, the effect, that a very short video file is triggered again and again and we experience very fast repetitions in the video, so that neither volume nor intensity do decrease:

Example 16: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 54–60.

A sudden contrast arises in bar 96 when the video image suddenly runs in slow motion:

Example 17: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 95–102.

Bar 96 is a brief moment of silence. It is inevitable to also mention bar 112:

The image shows a musical score for MIDI, spanning bars 110 to 114. The score is written in a complex, multi-measure format with various time signatures (3/4, 2/4, 3/8, 4/4) and dynamic markings. Key annotations include 'play twice (113-127)', 'play 5 times', and '(LIVE-CAMERA ON/OFF)'. The notation includes eighth notes, sixteenth notes, and rests, with some notes marked with '8va' and 'left'. The score is presented in a single system with a MIDI label on the left.

Example 18: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, bars 110–114.

In bar 112 the live camera is switched on. We no longer see the previously recorded video of an anonymous pianist, but the back of the pianist performing live on stage. It is a moment of irritation or surprise, well placed at this point. The pianist continues to play, but nothing is audible anymore. This moment is also kind of comedic, considering the fact, that the pianist continues to play in a very virtuoso manner, but everything is silent. It's a moment of further alienation: Now that the real pianist is finally showing up in the video, there is no sound. It is as if the real pianist is simply not able to create his own sound without help of his faceless avatar. So when bars 112-126 (see Example 18) are repeated, the live camera is switched off again and the avatar appears again on the screen. Just before the end, c8 (Prins, Fig. 4) respectively C7/180 (Bogner, Table 2) is played on the keyboard. This results in a fixed transposition of 64 semitones and thus in a dramatic acceleration of the video sample, preparing the end of the first piece of this cycle *Piano Hero. An immersive cycle for midi-keyboard, grand piano, live cameras, video and live electronics*.

The image shows a musical score for MIDI, spanning bars 158 to the end. The score is written in a complex, multi-measure format with various time signatures (3/4, 2/4, 3/8, 4/4) and dynamic markings. Key annotations include 'loco' and '5'. The notation includes eighth notes, sixteenth notes, and rests, with some notes marked with '8va' and 'left'. The score is presented in a single system with a MIDI label on the left.

Example 19: PRINS. *Piano Hero#1*, end.

As a summary of this analysis, *Piano Hero #1* is an attention-demanding piece throughout. It is a piece that constantly confronts the listener and the viewer with new audio and video information. However, the frame and the main motif remain unchanged. It is always the torso of a pianist standing in front of the open body of a piano with or without objects in his hands. The sounds are directly related to the gestures of the video avatar, but the gestures that the pianist performs on stage are detached from the sounds. We not only experience an alienation from sound, but also from the performer. The actual performer fades into the background, becoming a "machinist".¹¹⁹ Additionally the avatar's face is never visible in the video and therefore remains far, strange, anonymous, unfamiliar and unknown. The appearance of the score corresponds to a normal piano score, since the score is notated in a normal piano system. However, the playing styles of the piano are different to what one expect from a piano score, which is because the keys only produce the sound indirectly as trigger for sounds previously recorded in a video. What we hear in the video recordings are noises. The typical way of producing sound on a piano is omitted.¹²⁰ Also typical playing techniques such as chordal playing do not appear in this score. In contrast to Michael Beil's *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape*, which I will examine in the next chapter, *Piano Hero #1* is a monophonic composition.

¹¹⁹ BOGNER 2016, p. 9.

¹²⁰ See: Ibid., p. 9.

5.2 Michael Beil – Key Jack/Key Jane

Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape by Michael Beil was premiered in January 2017 in Ghent by Frederic Croene and has a duration of 13 minutes. Performances by women may also be called *Key Jane*.¹²¹ Musicologist Rebecca Diependaele writes:

"Key Jack has become a trademark of Michael Beil (°1963) to thoroughly dismantle the traditional image of the musician and his instrument. In Key Jack, the grand piano has even disappeared from the stage altogether. Deprived of his beloved instrument, the pianist has exchanged his black suit for a more casual outfit. Once a soloist, he is now assisted by 2 questionable Doppelgänger. Yet, Key Jack is still a highly virtuosic solo piano piece. In front of the camera the pianist faces a mind-bending playback-challenge. Beil thereby skillfully recombines movement, image and sound, thus confusing even the most alert spectators. The result is a fascinating performance, that almost makes you forget the piano isn't actually there."¹²²

There are some parallels to Stefan Prins' *Piano Hero #1*. Both compositions address the act of piano playing itself. Another similarity is that the use of video plays an important role in conveying the artistic position of the composer. Besides, *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* is also dedicated to Frederic Croene, to whom Stefan Prins' dedicated *Piano Hero #1*.

One of the differences to Stefan Prins' *Piano Hero #1* is that Michael Beil uses the entire "keyboard" almost excessively, additionally supported by video technology, as we will see later. I am writing "keyboard" in quotation marks, because the pianist in Michael Beil's *Key Jack* no longer plays on any kind of keyboard at all. The pianist's fingers are running over an empty table top.

¹²¹ See: <https://www.michael-beil.com/#/key-jack>, accessed 02.06.2024.

¹²² See: Ibid., accessed 02.06.2024.

5.2.1 The invisible piano

There are several compositions that refer to the piano without actually using the piano. Among compositions that are similar to *Key Jack* in the sense that they are not played on a physical piano is for example *Music from Somewhere for pianist's hands, lights and stereo audio tape* by Fran MM Cabeza de Vaca, written in 2017 and reviewed in 2019.¹²³ Haize Lizarazu, a pianist, experimental musician and artistic researcher, interpreted both pieces and developed an entire concert program entitled "Pianist without Piano".¹²⁴ In her article "Pre-gesture, gesture and sound on (no) piano: Music from Somewhere", Concerning *Music from Somewhere* Lizarazu wrote:

"During the performance of the piece, no piano is there to respond with a resulting sound, or to feel its physical resistance. Therefore, the study process goes back to the real piano; not to practising the score itself, but to practising the feeling, the perception of playing those different piano scores. [...] Hence, the focus of the practice process relies on the awareness of your own body."¹²⁵

It is an interesting coincidence that both compositions begin with "clicking" sounds. In the case of *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* it is the sonified blinking of the eyes; not really a gesture, but a reflex, that usually doesn't receive attention, yet happens permanently. Additionally, the blinking of the eyes, a reflex that usually is not controlled, now has to be controlled in time and is becoming not only visually but also sonically meaningful. The video is of crucial importance. Without video, the blinking of the eyes would not be that noticeable as an also musically relevant element. In *Music from Somewhere* switching on and off of a light at the beginning of the piece is accompanied by similar clicking sounds as the blinking of the eyes in *Key Jack*, being the first visual and acoustic source.

¹²³ See: LIZARAZU 2022, Introduction.

¹²⁴ See: <https://www.michael-beil.com/one>, accessed 02.06.2024.

¹²⁵ LIZARAZU 2022, p. 23.

5.2.2 Max patch

The main patch is called "_MIVA Key Jack 1.1. M1 2022.maxpat" and has the following appearance in presentation mode:

Fig. 15: "_MIVA Key Jack 1.1. MA 2022.maxpat".

In the abstraction "KJmanual" Michael Beil has summarized some basic instructions for using the patch:

Fig. 16: "KJmanual.maxpat".

These instructions don't tell us much about how the patch works, but it is clear that the operation should ultimately be simple, similar to the main patch for Piano Hero #1, and that if executed correctly, the performer only needs to press the space bar once to start and stop the score and the Esc key to stop all processes.

The score that is started by pressing the space bar once is the following text file:


```
0 label 1
0 fadeall 0 0
0 ram record 0 24000
24000 ram record 24500 10000
12000 ram record 35000 4500
7500 ram record 40000 8000
4000 plane 1 fade 1 0
0 ram player 1 play 0 24000 2
6000 ram record 48500 6000
3000 plane 2 fade 1 0
0 ram player 2 play 35000 4500 0.5
3000 ram record 55000 6000
0 ram player 1 play 24500 10000 2
6000 ram record 61500 5000
0 ram player 2 play 48500 6000 0.5

4000 label 2
0 ram player 1 play 40000 8000 2
6000 ram player 2 play 50500 3000 -0.5
2000 ram player 1 play 40000 8000 -2
4000 fadeall 0 0
2250 ram record 67000 18000
20250 plane 1 fade 1 0
0 ram player 1 play 0 24000 2
2250 ram record 85500 9000
4735 ram player 1 play 40000 8000 2
2015 plane 2 fade 1 0
0 ram player 2 play 35000 4500 0.5
3000 ram record 95000 9000
0 ram player 1 play 24500 10000 2
5015 ram player 1 play 24500 10000 -2
0 ram player 2 play 35000 4000 -0.5
6235 ram record 104500 13000
6985 ram player 2 play 49500 5000 -0.5

4015 label 3
2000 plane 1 fade 0 0
0 ram record 118000 2500
2000 ram player 2 play 61500 4576 0.5
8000 ram record 121000 4500
1125 ram player 2 play 35500 2250 0.5
4500 plane 1 fade 1 0
0 plane 2 fade 0 0
0 ram player 1 play 875 9125 1
1125 ram record 126000 2250
3375 ram record 129000 2250
2625 plane 2 fade 1 0
0 ram player 2 play 35000 4500 0.5
750 ram record 132000 3625
1265 ram player 1 play 24500 10000 2
4985 ram player 1 play 118000 2000 1
2000 plane 1 fade 0 0
0 plane 2 fade 0 0
```

Fig. 17: "Keyjack 1.4.txt" (excerpt).

If you are curious and want to find out where this text file is actually loaded, you first have to exit presentation mode and the patch will look like this:

Fig. 18: Main patch, no presentation view.

Double click on the purple colored subpatch "p controls" (see Figure 16) you find the subpatch "controls":

Fig. 19: subpatch "p controls".

And in this subpatch the subpatch "p readscore", where the textfile is loaded as a message:

Fig. 20: subpatch "p readscore".

The textfile (see Fig. 17), loaded in the subpatch "p readscore" (see Fig. 19) is the actual score, consisting of messages, that are received and interpreted somewhere else in the patch, for example the "label"-numbers are received and interpreted in the subpatch "label" and have a structuring function that correlates with the rehearsal numbers. Fig. 14 is just a small excerpt of the score. There are 16 labels in total. Or the "plane" commands are received in the subpatch "fade&co" (see Fig. 21) and influence the brightness of the video screenings (see Fig. 22).

Fig. 21: subpatch "gotolabel".

Fig. 22: subpatch "p fade&co".

In his email, Michael Beil mentioned some other elements of the text file and other interesting, also technical, aspects of such an intermedial work:

"The file called Keyjack 1.4.txt contains all the commands that are processed automatically while the piece is running. Each line begins with a number, which is the distance in milliseconds from the last command. If there is a zero, then the commands are issued one after the other. The commands are forwarded to the corresponding work areas in Max via a route object. For example, if it says *vrec*, then a video recording is started with a specific length, which is saved at a specific location in a video buffer. *vplay* triggers a playback process; a specific point from the video buffer is played for a specific time in milliseconds and at a specific speed on one of the two projection surfaces."¹²⁶

A line of the textfile could for example be read like that:

"7500 ram records 40000 8000"

means that it is recorded into the buffer from 40000 ms for 8000 ms.

"0 RAM player 2 play 35000 4500 0.5"

means that the buffer is played at half speed from 35000 ms for 4500 ms

etc.

The patch is very complex, but at the same time very clear and well structured. It is also practical that for rehearsals there is the text file "KJziffern.txt" with which you can jump to rehearsal marks that are also marked in the actual score for the pianist (see Example 20).

¹²⁶ BEIL in a private communication (mail, 02.06.2024), orig.: "Das File mit dem Namen *Keyjack 1.4.txt* enthält alle Befehle, die automatisch abgearbeitet werden während das Stück läuft. Jede Zeile beginnt mit einer Zahl, das ist der Abstand in Millisekunden vom letzten Befehl. Wenn da eine Null steht, dann werden die Befehle direkt nacheinander ausgegeben. Die Befehle werden in Max über ein *route* Objekt in die entsprechenden Arbeitsbereiche weitergeleitet. Wenn da zum Beispiel *vrec* steht, dann wird eine Videoaufnahme gestartet mit einer bestimmten Länge, die an einer ganz bestimmten Stelle in einem Videobuffer gespeichert wird. *vplay* löst einen Abspielvorgang aus, hier wird eine bestimmte Stelle aus dem Videobuffer für eine bestimmte Zeit in Millisekunden und in einem bestimmten Tempo auf einer der beiden Projektionsflächen abgespielt.", translated by the author.

5.2.3 Score analysis

In this chapter I will carry out the score analysis. I will pay particular attention to the musical material used and worked out in this composition, based on the score "Key Jack 3.0 2018.pdf", the video file "Key Jack Gent Doku.mov", the click track "Key Jack click.wav" and the playback "Key Jack Tape.wav".¹²⁷

As already mentioned in chapter 5.2.1, the composition begins with the blinking of the eyes. The blinking is rhythmically notated as can be seen in Score Example 20. The notation reminds of percussion notation:

Key Jack
for pianist with live-video and tape Michael Beil 2016

The score consists of three systems: right video, left video, and live player. The right video system is in 2/4 time with a tempo of quarter note = 60. The left video system is also in 2/4 time and includes a 'videorec 24000 ms' box. The live player system is in 2/4 time and features rhythmic notation for five 'blink' events, with the first labeled 'blink (with the sound)'. A box labeled 'basic position** green*' is placed above the first blink notation.

Example 20: BEIL. *Key Jack*, beginning.

The score consists of three systems, one for the live player, one for the left video and one for the right video. The live player starts in "basic position**" that is described as: "**hand on the board / view towards cam, lean a little bit forward with a nasty grin".¹²⁸ Michael Beil also writes that it has to be "always EXACTLY the same position for cuts in the video".¹²⁹ Color names like "green*" refer to different colors of hats being changed during the composition: "you need three hats in different colors: in the score as green/red/blue".¹³⁰

¹²⁷ See appendices, in folder: "Key Jack".

¹²⁸ See: BEIL 2016, p. 1.

¹²⁹ See: Ibid., p.1.

¹³⁰ See: Ibid. p. 1.

Since the piece has to be played by heart¹³¹, the click track plays an important role. The click track is not only a reference for the tempo, but also contains additional instructions, such as when to blink, when to turn the head, when and what to play and so on.

Besides blinking or changing the hats, other important elements to be carried out performatively are turning the head, as can be seen in Example 21:

Example 21: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 13–16.

And the flip of the fingers as can be seen in bar 25 of Example 22:

Example 22: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 21–25.

Always synchronously with the flip of the fingers, a video is turned on or off. Here it is the left video at bar 25. In the video we see the recorded blinking of the eyes that the live performer previously performed and hear the clicking sounds associated with it. The video recording is played at double speed, so that the blinking of the eyes and the associated clicking sounds occurs now not only in every second bar, as was the case at the beginning (see Example 20), but in every bar:

¹³¹ See: BEIL 2016.

Example 23: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 26–30.

The first, if you like to say so, "variation" of a motif – the blinking of the eyes is the motif here – is created by changing the playback speed. With another flip of the fingers in bar 30 (see Example 23), also the right video is projected, so that at the end of the first page both videos are projected:

Fig. 23: video still image "Key Jack Gent Doku.mov", live.

Fig. 24: video still image "Key Jack Gent Doku.mov", live and left.

Fig. 25: video still image "Key Jack Gent Doku.mov", live, left, right.

Up to this point on sonic level we hear various clicking sounds (blinking of the eyes, flip of the fingers) and a kind of constant windy background sound. The next sound event is surprising for various reasons. It is the sound of a heavily edited, kind of robotic sounding voice, claiming "I'm Key Jack saviour of the real world"¹³²:

Example 24: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 34–36.

Especially in combination with the "nasty grin"¹³³ that is explicitly requested by the composer, this text appears kind of absurd and humorous, not only in terms of content, but also supported by the strong distortion. Above all, especially in combination with the two video projections, the question immediately arises: What is the "real world"? This question becomes all the more relevant as the live performer, representing the "real world", so to say, is banned into darkness with a flip of the fingers, now executed in the right video:

¹³² See: BEIL 2016, p. 2.

¹³³ See: Ibid., p. 1.

Fig. 26: video still image "Key Jack Gent Doku.mov", left and right.

Light is switched on again with a synchronous flip of the fingers in the right and left video in bar 41 (see Example 25). The live performer appears again, who in turn switches off his two duplicates with a flip of his fingers in bar 42:

Example 25: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 38–42.

From here the pianist finally begins to play on the tabletop. The finger movements are very clearly audible because they are also in the fixed media. The musical material that the pianist must play on the tabletop is one-handed scales in intervals of fourths with the instructions "watch and follow the playing fingers. try do the real fingering" and "play very clearly by lifting fingers as high as possible" (see Example 26, bar 45):

lv 43

rv

videorec 18000 ms

left hand to playing position as late as possible

turn view to the left like waiting to take over hands remain in basic position

play on board (no sound) m.s.*

live

*watch and follow the playing fingers, try to do the real fingering play very clearly by lifting fingers as high as possible

Example 26: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 43–45.

Practicing scales in different intervals is a common practice method and essential part of pianist training. Playing scales is also often used to warm up fingers and to "get to know" the touch and sound of a new instrument. Shortly before the scales begin the tempo of the click track that has before been quarter = 60 rapidly jumps to quarter = 160 (see Example 25, bar 42). The scale is played up and down with the hands taking over from each other as in Example 27, bar 47:

lv 46

rv

live

m.d.*

*watch and follow the playing fingers, try to do the real fingering play very clearly by lifting fingers as high as possible

Example 27: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 46&47.

In *Key Jack*, in contrast to *Piano Hero #1*, the pianist plays what is typical for piano playing. The practice material becomes musical material, but it doesn't sound yet.

Flipping the fingers is repeatedly used to either turn the right or left video projection or the light for the live performer on and off (see Example 28, bar 52) and in bar 53 (see Example 28, bar 53) new musical material is introduced:

Example 28: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 51–53.

The pianist must play octave jumps in quarter triplets on the empty table top, as if playing over almost the entire register of a piano. The octave jumps then transition into tone repetitions (see Example 29) which should be played "like a hamster with both index fingers and clear movements":¹³⁴

Example 29: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 57–59.

Exactly at the moment when the tone repetitions begin (Example 29, bar 58), there is an interesting synchronization point between the two video pianists. They both turn their heads towards the live performer as if to watch him play. It is the first moment in which something like an awareness of the existence of the "alter egos" is shown.

The next musical material to be introduced is full chords, with the instruction to play them in *ffff* (see Example 30), which is interesting, because you still can't hear anything except of the sound of the fingertips on the table top, the windy background sound and clicking sounds of the blinking of the eyes and flipping of the fingers.

¹³⁴ See: BEIL 2016, p. 4.

Example 30: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 63&64.

It is therefore rather the pianist's gesture that implements the *ffff* by making very large arm movements. This type of movement reminds me e.g., at the opening chords of a Tchaikovsky piano concerto or similar virtuoso piano works. The chords are built by octave layers that start on different pitches, so that now different interval layers appear (see Example 30).

Now that the scales, octave jumps, tone repetition and chords have been introduced as musical material, they are being processed, after a short interruption (see Example 31) in which we hear again the very distorted voice, played in half speed, explaining "I'm Key Jack saviour of the real world":

Example 31: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 68–71.

It is noticeable that tempo plays an important role. The different speeds at which material is presented, have major impact on the perception. This is not only applied to the playback speeds, but also to the live performer.

From bar 94 to bar 95, the scales are passed on from the live performer to the virtual pianist. The live performer already used the full width of his image section. This restriction is now lifted, as the virtual pianists can continue the scale into higher or lower registers:

Example 32: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 94&95.

The three pianists are now really playing together and becoming a unit. From this moment on we hear a piano sound for the first time. The somewhat raw midi sound quality fits the composition, because it corresponds to the technical playing style. Now it becomes also clear why turning the head was necessary. Whenever a scale is passed from one player to another, the pianists face the direction in which the scale continues. As the music progresses, the linear direction is broken, parallel- and countermovements occur through simultaneous playing:

Example 33: BEIL. *Key Jack*, countermovement.

In Example 33 the live performer and the pianist in the left video projection play at the same time a scale in countermovement. In a further step of agglomeration, all three pianists play at the same time:

Example 34: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bar 110.

In Example 34 the scales are played in parallel movement by the two virtual pianists, but the real pianist plays the octave jumps in a faster tempo than before, i.e. in eighth note triplets instead of quarter note triplets. The octave jumps are then, just as the scales before, passed on from pianist to pianist:

Example 35: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bar 111.

In Example 35 we can see the pianist in the right video taking over the octave jumps from the live pianist and the live pianist and the pianist in the left video are playing the scales in countermovement. This type of arrangement continues until all three pianists finally come together in bar 117 with the same musical material:

Example 36: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bar 117.

Similar to the scales and the octaves the chords are then added to the music. They are also played faster than before and passed on from pianist to pianist, while the other musical material, i.e. the octave jumps, is still preserved. All of this finally culminates in a climax in bar 136 (see Example 37) where all pianists play chords:

Example 37: BEIL. *Key Jack*, bars 135–138.

Acceleration and deceleration continue. The chords oscillate between half note values and quarter note values.

Example 38: BEIL. *Key Jack*, chords.

The 3/4, respectively 3/2 time signature, is an anticipation of the last major section of this composition, which will begin in bar 282, as a waltz, after a middle section that brings completely different musical material, such as smaller, figurative motifs consisting of alternating notes, random notes or extended glissandos (see Examples 39 and 40 on the next page):

279

lv

rv

right (beater)

live 14 to basic

left

Example 39: BEIL. *Key Jack*, end of middle section.

282 bar 250 16000 ms

lv

rv freeze

right (fist)

live videorec 71875 ms until bar 398 =96 play confidently with clear movements of both hands

*

Example 40: BEIL. *Key Jack*, beginning of waltz.

6 Interpretation

In the preface to *Intermedialität von Bild und Musik* the editors of the book write that "compound word and concept formations that are combined with the prefix 'Trans' and 'Inter' are currently popular in the history of science to signal the willingness to collaborations that go beyond the boundaries of disciplines and media."¹³⁵

Music in particular, as the editors write, would have always been oriented towards other art genres with a tendency to legitimize itself through this and as a negative result in the 20th century, the suspicion of "pseudomorphosis" arose.¹³⁶

For this reason, among others, I have selected works whose discussion made it clear that both the musical level and the video level are inextricably linked and that the work itself could not exist without one or the other. In both cases, the video is not just a purely illustrative element added to the music, but has crucial thematic significance. I would like to emphasize that the following impressions are a personal reflection.

6.1 Reality vs. virtuality

In *Key Jack* we saw a pianist, surrounded by two virtual video-doppelgangers, who, with a strange grin, claims that he is the savior of the real world. However, the space of the "real world" that is available to him in this special set-up, seems to be too small, so that the music has to be continued by his two virtual doppelgangers. The question is whether the video-doppelgangers are hindering due to the limitation of space or supporting the pianist by playing what the pianist himself cannot play. This question can also be asked in a media theoretical discussion. If media are an extension of human beings, are they basically

¹³⁵ OY-MARRA et al. (2008), preface, orig.: "Zusammengesetzte Wort- und Begriffsbildungen, die sich mit dem Präfix 'Trans' und 'Inter' verbinden, haben gegenwärtig wissenschaftsgeschichtlich Konjunktur, um die Bereitschaft zu einer Zusammenarbeit zu signalisieren, die über die Grenzen der Disziplinen und der Medien hinausgeht.", translated by the author.

¹³⁶ See: Ibid., preface.

supportive by performing tasks that would otherwise be impossible? An additional ironic aspect is the fact that the pianist himself is not able to produce any tone at all, because he only plays on a table top.

The same applies to the pianist in Stefan Prins' *Piano Hero #1*. The pianist is also obviously unable to produce any sound at all without the help of his virtual avatar. So it is obvious that the piece could not work without the video layer, since the entire sound comes from the prerecorded videos. Therefore, I think that these two compositions are excellent examples of "intermediality" as described in Chapter 1.

6.2 Tradition and stability vs. new approaches and flexibility

It is interesting that both compositions refer to the piano at least in the broadest sense. The piano is one of the instruments probably most associated with tradition and stability, whereas in media everything changes quickly. We also saw from the patches that they are actually in constant development, need revisions, updates and therefore a certain flexibility.

Multimedia compositions seem to be more in motion. For example by having all files available in folders online, theoretically changes could easily be made, files and scores revised and exchanged, etc.

Florian Bogner also mentioned concerns about the re-performability in the long term under changing technical conditions.¹³⁷ Michael Beil pointed out that one should use Max 8.3 or above.¹³⁸ Softwares must be kept up to date. Composers will maybe own the most common softwares, but it cannot automatically be assumed that this applies to all performers. Therefore, chances might be, that performances might remain reserved for a relatively small circle of specialized performers. Furthermore performances of multimedia

¹³⁷ See: BOGNER 2016, p. 7.

¹³⁸ See appendices: KJmanual.maxpat, in folder: Key Jack.

compositions depend on the equipment of concert halls and also on the availability of sound engineers and video technicians who eventually need to be paid extra and so on and so forth.

6.3 The "allround-composer" or the collective?

To develop compositions like the compositions discussed in this thesis, composers need to be familiar with questions that used to belong into the area of sound engineers or programmers. They need to be familiar with the technical aspects in order to achieve the desired aesthetic result. They not only need to provide well mixed playbacks or patches for live-electronics or live-videos, but should also be able to give precise instructions and technical riders. Therefore composers might often work closely together with programmers, sound engineers or visual artists. In the credits to *Piano Hero #1* Stefan Prins mentions that he worked with Klaas Verpoest to program the Max Patch and the video was filmed by Kobe Wens.¹³⁹ Working in collectives of experts in their fields can be helpful and inspiring and cultivate synergies that transcend the boundaries of individual artistic practices. The question of dependencies and weighting could provide interesting potential for discussion.

¹³⁹ See: PRINS 2011, p. 3.

Conclusion

The use of instruments in combination with audio and video playback or live-electronics and live-video has become commonplace, but compositions as *Piano Hero #1 for midi-keyboard, live-electronics and video* (2011 – 12) by Stefan Prins and *Key Jack for pianist without piano with live-video and tape* (2016/2018) by Michael Beil incorporate these technologies. By incorporating technology, composers can expand the sound palette and increase the expressive potential. Synchronized use of different media can enhance the overall aesthetic experience and deepen the audience's engagement with the performance. The complexity no longer just lies in the music itself, but also in how different media are connected. Multimedia compositions are often based on and inspired from non-musical topics. They often clearly address socially relevant, sometimes political issues in a direct way that would not be possible through music alone due to the abstract nature of music. With this characteristic multimedia compositions often seem to stand in opposition to what is known as "absolute music."

When I observe contemporary tendencies, even beyond music, I notice an increasing level of technology. I'm also speaking of rather profound affairs as in communication and other daily routines. In art, artistic decisions sometimes are handed over to technology, e.g., an artificial intelligence. This brings advantages such as saving time, but perhaps it is also appropriate to ask what we are giving away and if the technological acceleration might from time to time need a counterpoint.

Abstract

This thesis explores the development of technological advancements and sound-aesthetic considerations in relation to the fundamental requirements of creating and perceiving music, specifically the interplay between composers, performers, audiences, technologies. New technologies not only influence the requirements of notation and interpretation but also reshape the perception of music. In an era characterized by media saturation, – even in situations beyond the realm of the arts –, audiences might increasingly expect dynamic and multi-sensory experiences. Intermedial elements within a compositional framework can lead to synergistic relationships, resulting in heightened aesthetic complexity and emotional impact. Such works can contribute to critically questioning or even offering temporary explanations for certain realities of life and art.

By examining the interplay between technologies, compositional approaches, and musical output and perception, this thesis aims to gain insights into the evolution of music. It will primarily focus on the interaction between visual arts and music composition. The convergence of visual and auditory elements creates experiences that engage multiple senses simultaneously. Limiting the study to works that are similar in terms of instrumentation allows for direct comparison of different approaches and implementations. Understanding how different elements converge and interact can provide valuable insights into creative processes. Overall, this thesis aims to deepen the understanding of the interplay of different artistic media in the composition process and the potential for synergistic creativity.

Abstract (German)

Diese Arbeit untersucht die Entwicklung technologischer Fortschritte und klangästhetischer Überlegungen in Bezug auf die grundlegenden Anforderungen des Schaffens und Wahrnehmens von Musik, insbesondere das Zusammenspiel zwischen KomponistInnen, InterpretInnen, Publikum und Technologien. Neue Technologien beeinflussen nicht nur die Anforderungen an Notation und Interpretation, sondern verändern auch die Wahrnehmung von Musik. In einer Zeit der Medienübersättigung – auch in Situationen jenseits der Kunst – könnte es sein, dass das Publikum zunehmend dynamische und multisensorische Erlebnisse erwartet. Intermediale Elemente innerhalb eines kompositorischen Rahmens können zu synergetischen Beziehungen führen, die zu einer erhöhten ästhetischen Komplexität und emotionalen Wirkung führen. Solche Arbeiten können dazu beitragen, bestimmte Lebens- und Kunstwirklichkeiten kritisch zu hinterfragen oder sogar vorläufige Erklärungen anzubieten.

Durch die Untersuchung des Zusammenspiels zwischen Technologien, kompositorischen Ansätzen sowie musikalischem Output und musikalischer Wahrnehmung zielt diese Arbeit darauf ab, Einblicke in die Entwicklung der Musik zu gewinnen. Der Fokus liegt vor allem auf der Interaktion zwischen visueller Kunst und Musikkomposition. Die Konvergenz von visuellen und auditiven Elementen schafft Erlebnisse, die mehrere Sinne gleichzeitig ansprechen. Die Beschränkung der Untersuchung auf Werke mit ähnlicher Instrumentierung ermöglicht einen direkten Vergleich unterschiedlicher Ansätze und Umsetzungen. Das Verständnis, wie verschiedene Elemente zusammenlaufen und interagieren, kann wertvolle Einblicke in kreative Prozesse liefern. Insgesamt zielt diese Arbeit darauf ab, das Verständnis für das Zusammenspiel verschiedener künstlerischer Medien im Kompositionsprozess und das Potenzial für synergetische Kreativität zu vertiefen.

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PH1-MacOS12-Max8 (as folder on USB)

Key Jack (as folder on USB)

ERKLÄRUNG ZUR EINHALTUNG DER GUTEN WISSENSCHAFTLICHEN PRAXIS

Zu- und Vorname: Al-Dayaa, Afamia

Matrikelnummer: 01174111

Studienrichtung,
Studienzweig bzw.
Universitätslehrgang: UT 504 Komposition und Musiktheorie; Medienkomposition u. Angew. Musik (Stzw)

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2) Mir sind die studienrechtlichen Bestimmungen und die Regeln der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis, die im Universitätsgesetz 2002, im Satzungsteil Studienrecht und in den Richtlinien des Rektorats (Richtlinie des Rektorats zur Akademischen Integrität, Richtlinie des Rektorats zur Künstlerischen Diplom-/Masterarbeit und Richtlinie des Rektorats für wissenschaftliche Arbeiten) enthalten sind, bekannt. Ich bestätige hiermit deren Einhaltung.

3) Mir ist bekannt, dass wissenschaftliches Fehlverhalten zivil- und/oder strafrechtliche Konsequenzen nach sich ziehen kann. Zudem verpflichte ich mich unwiderruflich, die mdw schad- und klaglos zu halten im Falle der Geltendmachung von - insbesondere aber nicht ausschließlich - urheberrechtlichen oder urheberrechtlich abgeleiteten Ansprüchen durch Dritte gegenüber der mdw.

4) Ich versichere, dass ich die Arbeit selbst verfasst habe. Dort, wo ich andere Arbeiten verwendet habe, wurden diese von mir als wörtlich oder inhaltlich übernommene Stellen zitiert. Andere als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel habe ich nicht benutzt.

5) Ich versichere, dass ich diese Arbeit im In- oder Ausland weder zum Teil noch als Ganzes in irgendeiner Form als künstlerische oder wissenschaftliche Master-/Diplomarbeit, Dissertation oder sonstige Abschlussarbeit vorgelegt habe.

6) Ich bestätige, dass meine vorgelegte gebundene Arbeit mit der eingereichten elektronischen Fassung vollkommen übereinstimmt.

12.06.2024

Datum

Unterschrift der/des Studierenden

HINWEISE:

Universitätsgesetz 2002

Begriffsbestimmungen

§ 51 (2)

Z 31 Ein Plagiat liegt jedenfalls dann vor, wenn Texte, Inhalte oder Ideen übernommen und als eigene ausgegeben werden. Dies umfasst insbesondere die Aneignung und Verwendung von Textpassagen, Theorien, Hypothesen, Erkenntnissen oder Daten durch direkte, paraphrasierte oder übersetzte Übernahme ohne entsprechende Kenntlichmachung und Zitierung der Quelle und der Urheberin oder des Urhebers.

Z 32 Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen liegt jedenfalls dann vor, wenn jemand unerlaubte Hilfsmittel benutzt oder sich bei der Verfassung einer schriftlichen Arbeit oder Ablegung einer Prüfung oder bei der Erstellung einer künstlerischen Arbeit unerlaubter Weise einer anderen Person bedient (insbesondere Inanspruchnahme einer von einer dritten Person erstellten Auftragsarbeit) oder wenn Daten und Ergebnisse erfunden oder gefälscht werden.

Nichtigerklärung von Beurteilungen

§ 73 (1) Das für studienrechtliche Angelegenheiten zuständige Organ hat die Beurteilung mit Bescheid für nichtig zu erklären, wenn

1. bei einer Prüfung die Anmeldung zu dieser Prüfung erschlichen wurde oder
2. bei einer Prüfung oder einer wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Arbeit die Beurteilung, ein Plagiat gemäß § 51 Abs 2 Z 31 oder durch Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen gemäß § 51 Abs 2 Z32, erschlichen wurde.

Widerruf inländischer akademischer Grade oder akademischer Bezeichnungen

§ 89 Der Verleihungsbescheid ist vom für die studienrechtlichen Angelegenheiten zuständigen Organ aufzuheben und einzuziehen, wenn sich nachträglich ergibt, dass der akademische Grad oder die akademische Bezeichnung insbesondere durch gefälschte Zeugnisse oder durch das Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen erschlichen worden ist. Bei Erweiterungsstudien ist das Abschlusszeugnis für nichtig zu erklären und einzuziehen, wenn sich nachträglich ergibt, dass der Abschluss insbesondere durch gefälschte Zeugnisse oder durch das Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen erschlichen worden ist.

Ghostwriting

§ 116a (1) Wer entgeltlich oder unentgeltlich ein Werk für eine andere Person herstellt oder einer anderen Person zur Verfügung stellt, ist, wenn sie oder er weiß oder nach den Umständen annehmen kann, dass dieses Werk in der Folge teilweise oder zur Gänze als Seminar-, Prüfungs-, oder Abschlussarbeit (Bachelorarbeit, wissenschaftliche oder künstlerische Arbeit) zum Nachweis nicht erbrachter eigenständiger Leistungen verwendet werden soll, mit Geldstrafe bis zu 25.000 Euro zu bestrafen.

Satzungsteil Studienrecht der mdw

Sicherung der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis

§ 38 (1) Die Studierenden haben die Regeln der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis einzuhalten. Gute wissenschaftliche Praxis bedeutet, im Rahmen der Aufgaben und Ziele der mdw die rechtlichen Regelungen, ethischen Normen und den aktuellen Erkenntnisstand des jeweiligen Faches einzuhalten (§ 51 Abs 2 Z 33 UG).

(2) Plagiate und anderes Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen – insbesondere im Rahmen von schriftlichen Seminar- und Prüfungsarbeiten, Bachelorarbeiten, wissenschaftlichen und künstlerischen Diplom- und Masterarbeiten sowie Dissertationen – sind dem im Rektorat für Lehre zuständigen Mitglied zu melden.

(3) Tritt während der Betreuungsphase ein Plagiat oder anderes Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen im Rahmen von Master- und Diplomarbeiten sowie Dissertationen auf, ist die Betreuerin oder der Betreuer berechtigt, die Betreuung zurückzulegen.

(4) Bei schwerwiegendem und vorsätzlichem Plagieren oder schwerwiegendem und vorsätzlichem anderen Vortäuschen von wissenschaftlichen oder künstlerischen Leistungen im Rahmen von Bachelor-, Master-, Diplomarbeiten oder Dissertationen kann das Rektorat über einen allfälligen Ausschluss vom Studium für höchstens zwei Semester mit Bescheid entscheiden.

(5) Jedenfalls müssen Studierende, die ein Fehlverhalten nach Abs 2 bis 4 setzen, vor Einreichung der Abschlussarbeit nachweislich eine Veranstaltung zur Sicherung der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis besuchen.

(6) Auf Abschlussarbeiten im Rahmen eines Universitätslehrganges sind die Bestimmungen für Diplom- und Masterarbeiten sinngemäß anzuwenden.

(7) Nähere Bestimmungen hat das Rektorat in einer Richtlinie festzulegen.

Richtlinien des Rektorats

Richtlinie des Rektorats zur Akademischen Integrität, Mitteilungsblatt Studienjahr 2019/20, 12. Stück, Nr. 176

Richtlinie des Rektorats zur Künstlerischen Diplom-/Masterarbeit, Mitteilungsblatt Studienjahr 2020/21, 21. Stück, Nr. 263

Richtlinie des Rektorats für wissenschaftliche Arbeiten, Mitteilungsblatt Studienjahr 2017/18, 3. Stück, Nr. 16

Leitfäden der Institute

Ergänzend zur "Richtlinie des Rektorats für wissenschaftliche Arbeiten" finden Sie hier die **Leitfäden der Institute** für die Erstellung der jeweiligen fachspezifischen Abschlussarbeiten.